

CO₂-SPICER - CO₂ Storage Pilot In a CarbonatE Reservoir

R2.5 Maps of basic petrophysical properties distribution in the storage complex

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CONTENT

1 INTRODUCTION.....	3
2 WELL LOGS EVALUATION.....	4
3 WELL LOGS UPSCALING.....	4
4 3D PETROPHYSICAL PROPERTIES DISTRIBUTION.....	6
REFERENCES.....	15

1 INTRODUCTION

After detailed interpretation of 3D seismic, construction of surfaces of key horizons and construction of the static reservoir model in Schlumberger Petrel software the petrophysical properties were distributed within the final model grid. The porosity and permeability were distributed in the reservoir facies zones (Vranovice Fm. and Nikolčice Fm.) in both segments, the main one covering directly the CO₂ injection structure and also in the larger segment covering the possible aquifer zone of Zar-3 storage (Fig. 1-1).

The basic input of for the reservoir properties in discrete wells were the well log results, which were interpreted for MND a.s. by Hrubý (2004, 2011) to provide the porosity and permeability values in reservoir intervals of the Žarošice field production wells. The wells in the aquifer part of reservoir within the model grid were re-interpreted in MND a.s.

Fig. 1-1: The working area of final 3D Zar-3 model grid including the Žarošice oil and gas field and its possible aquifer zone.

For the interpretation of petrophysical properties in the wells the PowerLog software was used in the oil and gas zone of Žarošice field and Interactive Petrophysics software in its possible aquifer part within the model grid.

2 WELL LOGS EVALUATION

The production wells logs were in detail interpreted for MND a.s. in 2004 and 2011 by Hrubý, the wells in the aquifer part of the model grid were interpreted recently to match the results of former interpretation. The Gamma Ray, Spontaneous Potential, Resistivity, Neutron log, Density and Sonic logs were used for log interpretation. These were complemented also by the Caliper log and NMR (nuclear magnetic resonance) data if available. The data were generally found as a good quality data by Hrubý (2004, 2011). For the temperature profile of the area the data from well tests and temperature logging were used and were available for the ZA3, UH3, ZA4A, ZA5H, ZA6 and ZA6A wells. For the porosity calculation several techniques were used (density – neutron crossplot – Fig 2-1, density, neutron, sonic) according to availability of the logs in discrete wells. The resulting porosity was corrected for the clay minerals presence and thus the final calculated porosities are effective ones. The water saturation S_w values were calculated from using the resistivity of the formation water, effective porosity, cementing factor and Archie's constant. The permeability was calculated using the effective porosity values and water saturation values using the Timur formula.

Fig. 2-1: Cross plot chart of PORN (neutron porosity) – HK (density).

3 WELL LOGS UPSCALING

17 wells including sidetracks, present within the area of interest where the reservoir facies of model zone Vranvice or Nikolčice Fm. were present were used for basic reservoir properties upscale process using property modelling module of Schlumberger Petrel. These wells were used - UH3, UH5, UH6, ZA1, ZA3, ZA4, ZA4A, ZA5H, ZA6, ZA6A, ZA7, ZA8AH, ZA8H, ZA9AH, ZA9H, ZA12 and ZA14H.

The well log interpretation described in chapter 2 were loaded to Petrel software and the upscale process was done separately for the effective porosity (PHIEQ) and

permeability (KABS) values with same arithmetic average method. The Upscale process was done in significant amount of iterations as for each grid change, each zone change or each change in layering the upscaling process has to be done individually. The Final well upscale example for the wells ZA3 and ZA4A is shown in Figs. 3-1 and 3-2.

Fig. 3-1: ZA3 depths, well logs and upscaled values of porosity (PHIEQ) and permeability (KABS).

Fig. 3-2: ZA4A depths, well logs and upscaled values of porosity (PHIEQ) and permeability (KABS).

4 3D PETROPHYSICAL PROPERTIES DISTRIBUTION

After the upscale of all available well logs within the model grid the distribution of porosity and permeability within the final model grid was done. As the static model dealing mostly with the carbonate type of reservoir in relatively large area with only locally denser dataset, the Gaussian sequential simulation was chosen as a property distribution method which is a stochastic method based on kriging but capable of capturing extreme values in a heterogenous reservoir. The properties should honour the wells results, histogram and variogram with same variability image over the model.

Fig. 4-1: The 3D view on first grid iteration (25 x 25 m) with 3D porosity distribution.

Fig. 4-2: The final iteration of 3D grid with porosity distributions (10 x 10 m horizontal grid + 1 m thickness of vertical layers).

Fig. 4-3: The reservoir engineering version of final iteration of 3D grid with porosity distributions (sub horizontal layering - 10 x 10 m horizontal grid + 1 m thickness of vertical layers).

Firstly the variograms and variogram maps were constructed and the anisotropy was tested for the dataset which was upscaled from the calculated well logs. Several major direction azimuths were tested in variograms ranging from the 0 – 35 degrees and anisotropy range was tested from 250 m to 2500 m in major direction and 150 m to 2500 m in minor direction using the spherical variogram. Finally as the only denser part of dataset is concentrated in the segment 2 covering only the direct vicinity of the Zar-3 CO₂ potential storage site and the data in the rest of the aquifer are rather scarce the isotropic distribution with the anisotropy range 1250 m in both directions was used for both reservoir zones. The distribution also was done in several iterations for different grid iterations. The first iteration of property modelling was done using the 25 x 25 m grid with 5 m layer interval in reservoir zones (Fig. 4-1) the last iterations were using horizontal grid density of 10x10 m with either 1 m layer thickness following the base of the reservoir zone (Fig. 4-2), or 1 m layer thickness with horizontal layering (Fig 4-3).

All different distributions were also gradually tested by reservoir engineers to match the known volume of hydrocarbons and to match the production results in the discrete parts of the grid penetrated by the production wells. Finally the 10 x 10 m grid with follow base layering was chosen as working one with the supplementary grid 10 x 10 m with horizontal layering. The resulting cross-sections of porosity and permeability distributions are demonstrated in Figs. 4-4 up to 4-7 and the maps of petrophysical properties in the working segment 2 area in Figs 4-8 up to 4-11. Finally the maps of average porosities and permeabilities were included. They are representing very simplified view of the 3D petrophysical properties distribution and cannot show the details of 3D porosity or permeability distribution, which can still be visualized and observed directly in 3D Schlumberger Petrel static model. The average porosities and permeabilities maps were exported for the standard 10 x 10 m grid (figs. 4-12 and 4-13) with the follow base layering and also for the 10 x 10 m grid with subhorizontal layering (figs. 4-14 and 4-15).

Fig. 4-4: Porosity distribution in 3D – J direction cross section – position at ZA6A well.

Fig. 4-5: Porosity distribution in 3D – J direction cross section – position at ZA3 well.

Fig. 4-6: Porosity distribution in 3D – J direction cross section – position at ZA9AH well.

Fig. 4-7: Porosity distribution in 3D – J direction cross section – position at ZA5H well.

Fig. 4-8: Permeability distribution map – K direction cross section – position in 3D in the lower right corner (grid level 1860 m at ZA6A).

Fig. 4-9: Permeability distribution map – K direction cross section – position in 3D in the lower right corner (grid level - 1815 m depth at ZA6A well).

Fig. 4-10: Porosity distribution map – K direction cross section – position in 3D in the lower right corner (grid level – 1815 m at ZA6A well).

Fig. 4-11: Porosity distribution map – K direction cross section – position in 3D in the lower right corner (grid level – 1860 m at ZA6A well).

Fig. 4-12: Average porosity map – calculated from final 3D grid 10x10 m with follow base layering.

Fig. 4-13: Average permeability map – calculated from final 3D grid 10x10 m with follow base layering.

Fig. 4-14: Average porosity map – calculated from final 3D grid 10x10 m with subhorizontal layering.

Fig. 4-15: Average permeability map – calculated from final 3D grid 10x10 m with subhorizontal layering.

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